

TRANSFORMING THE CONCEPT OF CUSTOMER ENGAGEMENT TO INCREASE BRAND LOYALTY

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Abstract:

Customer empowerment employs that customers need to feel valued so that they feel compelled to have brand loyalty. Two types of customer empowerment strategies have been distinguished: empowerment to better buying experience and create and empowerment to select. When the customers are provided with, they are also given the choice to determine the type of experience they would like to have with the brand, the actual empowerment takes place. Customer empowerment results in reduced costs because of substituting employee labour with customer input, less risk of product failure through ensured fit with customer preferences, but serves a niche market only. There has been an increased integration among the physical and digital world as the Covid imposed lockdowns forced the world indoors and brought a change in the needs, desires, habits, and routines of the customers. Brand loyalty can be increased in these pandemic times through transparency, value-based customer experiences and reverse rewarding.

Key Words: Covid, Imposed, Lockdowns, Customers

Introduction:

The customers of today have got endless options and are empowered enough to change their buying decisions and switch brands much faster. Digital technology development has provided power to customers to have remarkable influence on the marketing decisions. This strategy is utilised by various brands today like Lego and Swarovski are two of the visionary brands which allows the customers to not only create but also select and give preferences for their new product launches. The empowerment strategies could be of two different types: empowerment to create and empowerment to select (Fuchs and Schreier, 2011). Empowerment to create can be said to happen when the customers are asked to give their own ideas and designs to be used to develop new products and when we say empowerment to select, it means that individuals or potential customers are asked to select or vote between two or more options of the product which will then be taken at commercial level. The requirement for customer empowerment is important as it is required to make the customer feel so valued that they feel compelled to return to the same brand after considering multiple options to make a purchase decision. Initially, the emphasis of manufacturers and retailers used to be on using technology and training of employees to give a better customer experience. But the customer today has access to easy information at their fingertips and they undertake the buying decisions by taking into account information received not only from the sales team but also from a variety of sources which includes details from the website of the company, social media influencers, customer reviews and other related sites. So in a way, the customer becomes better informed than an average salesperson and on top of that, the product options are numerous along with minor variations which has resulted in a shift of power in the favour of customers and they can actually define how a company need to function which provides them with an empowerment essential for enabling companies to attain their business objectives. The days of hard-sell of products are giving way to the transition of companies towards empowering the customers to help them make knowledgeable decisions and become allies in the purchase process.

Customer Empowerment:

An advanced practice of customer empowerment refers to the transfer of brand decisions to customers themselves (Pranic & Roehl, 2012). Customer empowerment is supposed to happen when the customers are given not only the information but also the tools that are required to make the decision regarding the product. When the customers are provided with a better buying experience and they are also given the choice to determine the type of experience they would like to have with the brand, the actual empowerment takes place. What happens in this process is that a base of loyal customers is created who are provided added benefits in their purchase decisions. The basis for creating long term bonding with customers is to give emphasis to the impact being created by the product and to demonstrate the way product has aligned itself with the goals of the customer and help him in achieving success in those goals. Involving the customers in one way or the other helps companies cultivate a sense of participation by the customers which in turn helps gather authentic and actionable feedback which helps in cutting down the development cost as well as time. The word of mouth

generated results in creating enthusiasm about the product among future customers. Customer participation not only helps to acquire new customers but also generates an emotional connection with the buyer.

Importance of Customer Empowerment:

Customer empowerment helps companies in not only acquiring new customers but also in retaining existing customers. Studies have shown that if a company makes conscious efforts to empower the customer, the customer becomes more satisfied with brand experience. This not only helps with customer retention but also encourages customer advocacy. When customers feel supported by business and feels that the organization is aligned with their requirements, they develop a trust that the information received will be relevant for them. This encourages a level of dependency as the customer starts relying on business for decision making information as they trust that the company will suggest the best option as per their requirement. Here the customer service department can provide support for empowerment of the customer in achieving their goals and provide them excellent shopping experience. There are certain strategies which could be employed by customer service department for empowerment such as:

- **Self Service by customers:** If self-service tools are incorporated in the product service guidelines, it allows customers to search for solutions on their own and allows them to feel empowered to handle any challenge which comes up. Customer support team should create a knowledge base containing required information for troubleshooting and answer common questions which the customer can look through before reaching out to customer support whenever an issue comes up. It not only saves time for the customer but also for the support team.
- **Social Media:** This media has been at the forefront of bringing up awareness and empowerment among customers. With almost one third of customers today being less than 25 years of age, social media is a preferred channel for communication and its adoption has doubled in the pandemic times. The main reason is its power to connect remote customers through a digital platform. The media allows people to create or exchange information and provide comments which can be viewed by thousands of people. Hence even a single negative or positive comment which catches attention of social media can create changes in the fortune of the company. The consumer is aware of this power and has got the tools to utilize it. Hence it is necessary for a company to adopt social media related customer service and utilize it as a tool of empowerment and information to prevent development of any crisis.
- **Customer reviews and testimonials:** Apart from social media, customer review sites are also a platform where customers can raise their voices and opinions. It is important for a brand to have majorly positive customer reviews as negative comments can create a significant dent on the reputation of the company. As the majority of these sites do not provide an option to delete or edit the comments the customer service team need to be proactive in handling the situation and providing support for the grievances of the customers so that negative feedback can be changed by changing the perspective of the customer and giving him confidence that the company is willing to support the challenge faced an handle the request.
- **Collection of Customer Feedback:** Taking feedback from the customers after the purchase enables them to give their views about the product and shopping experience. There are various online tools available for collection of feedback which can then be analysed to understand the changes required to improve customer experiences. It also enables the company to see if they have satisfied customers and if not, what measures can be taken to add value to the shopping experience or product. Customers can be prompted to provide testimonials if they are willing to share the positive feedback.
- **Customer On boarding:** This can be described as a post purchase service and is essential to empower customers to get maximum value out of the product by providing instructions to correct usage of the consumer in learning to use the product properly. Customer on boarding empowers the customer as its product which results in saving time of the consumer in learning to use the product and avoids stress to display the usefulness of the product or service and the customer can be convinced that he has the right choice by purchasing the particular product.

Branding:

A brand is a name, term, design, symbol, or any other feature that identifies one seller's good or service a distinct from those of other sellers" (American Marketing Association). A brand can be defined as a set of tangible and intangible attributes designed to create awareness and identity, and to build the reputation of a product, service, person, place, or organization. The objective of a successful branding strategy is to create brands that can be differentiated from the competition, thereby reducing the number of perceived substitutes in the marketplace, increasing price elasticity, and improving profits. Branding strategies are built on the interdependent frameworks of competitive brand positioning, value chains development, and brand equity management. Competitive brand positioning requires the identification of a distinct market space and a cognitive location as perceived by consumers. (Tanya S, 2015). Branding however is defined as the process of creating a strong, positive perception of a company, its products, or services in the customer's mind after combining various elements like logo of the brand, its mission statement etc. Effective branding not only helps

the companies in creating a differentiation from similar products but also helps in building a loyal and long-standing customer base.

Brand Loyalty:

It is an accepted knowledge that in the highly diverse and vast market space available today, the competitive advantage is retained by the brand which has managed to earn loyalty of the consumers. However, brands also understand that traditional loyalty schemes and transaction-based rewards are no longer attractive for the customers. So, the brands today need to create more meaningful relationships and humanise the consumer interaction for gaining loyalty of customers. Some of the ways in which brand loyalty can be achieved in the modern times of pandemic are as follows:

- **Transparency:** With so much emphasis on data protection and privacy of online data, it has become essential to make clear attempts to maintain transparency by brands to maintain consumer loyalty. A few brands are making a conscious attempt to provide real time information like the courier companies, instead of just giving information on when a package will be delivered, providing real time tracking information which makes the consumer feel empowered and in control. It is also important for the information to be instantly available and fully reliable and innovative platforms need to be developed for the same. Loyalty can be achieved by an attempt by a brand to show the processes which used to be usually hidden and to keep the consumer constantly in loop. Profit margins of a firm used to be protected knowledge but now a few fashion brands have even started showing the pricing policy adopted to clearly showcase the margins and why the prices are different from similar brands in order to gain trust of customers.
- **Value based experiences:** Consumers are found to be more loyal to brands whose value system is more aligned to the individual values and aspirations. The brands today feel obliged to provide meaningful and rewarding experiences to the consumers to ensure their active engagement beyond the purchase decision. Fashion Brands are opting for sustainable, eco-friendly methods of production, raw material, recyclable packaging etc., to show that the company is making efforts to handle the issues which are close to the heart of customers.
- **Reverse Rewarding:** Rewards and point systems have been a traditional system of gaining the loyalty of customers. It brings the customers back to the company for repurchases to redeem the rewards. To align themselves with the desires of the customers, brands need to follow a more altruistic form of loyalty when the consumers choose to give back to society and to the planet rather than the individual customer. An example of this could be the collection of used cloth drives started by Big Bazaar to reward the customers for worn out clothes or plastic collection drives for recycling purposes which makes a brand look environment conscious.

These are some of the ways in which a brand can attempt to develop loyal relationships with the customers. Consumers are more aware of their own values and are inclined to align themselves with brands that suggest alliance to their own ethics, and they feel that the brand understands them as much as they understand the brands. As there is inclination towards customer empowerment, the brands need to understand the shift coming in and nurture a long-term relationship with the customer.

Need for Redefining Customer Empowerment:

To understand the need for redefining customer empowerment, we need to understand how the new age customer is changing. The availability of information at the fingertips and the pandemic situation has brought changes in the way consumers are taking their buying decisions. There has been an increased integration among the physical and digital world as the Covid imposed lockdowns forced the world indoors and brought a change in the needs, desires, habits, and routines of the customers. Even small shopkeepers learned to use social media for order booking and delivery purpose and major shopping shifted to online portals where physical verification of the product prior to purchase is not feasible. The customers learnt to use various devices for order placement and learned to get information through various sources from the virtual world. Safety became all too important and new societal norms are introduced to bring in a safe shopping experience.

In very simple terms, happier customers tend to be more loyal towards a brand. And this happiness comes when a customer feels in control of the buying experience and feel empowered by the brand as its values seems to align with the values of the customer. The customer not only feels rewarded but happier and valued to know that the brand cares for the changing requirements and desires of the customer. Empowerment and customer experience, these are the two things required for bringing out loyalty towards the brand in customer.

Conclusion:

So as the customer becomes more empowered, the Covid-19 pandemic has brought a visible shift in the desires, needs and routines of the customers. Speed and ease of shopping has been replaced by safety as priority. The lockdown brought its own rulebook and required brands to immediately evolve towards the changing priorities and requirements. The change in societal attitudes towards businesses started coming in much before the pandemic but now it is all the more important to put customer at the heart of the business and offer new services as per the consumer demand. It is perceived that people need to be empowered to do the right thing and

systems need to be developed to allow people to gather localised information and facilitate steps for betterment of the society. The current times are great for innovation and learning from the past mistakes as the pandemic has impacted all areas of our lives. The work from home culture created a new set of customers who were office based earlier and had no requirement of office setup at home. Once the offices reopen, the businesses will need to readapt themselves and empower customers and their own teams to re-imagine product requirement to build compelling customer experiences.

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